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Scoping review of global control strategies for *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato*

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (EG) causes cystic echinococcosis (CE), a neglected zoonotic disease with a global control burden in the billions of dollars. We provide a comprehensive overview of EG control interventions worldwide.

Methods: We followed the Arksey and O'Malley Framework. We identified and coded selected articles and classified the data based on target host, type of study, and control mechanism. We described each intervention's efficacy, safety, barriers, and facilitators. Critical appraisal was conducted independently by two reviewers using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool.

Results: We screened 7853 studies and analyzed seven on human interventions, 21 on animals, and 17 on both. Human studies focused mostly on educational strategies and monitoring. Animal studies focused predominantly on praziquantel (PZQ) for dogs and the EG95 vaccine for sheep. Animal and human studies were larger, longer, and covered wider areas. Overall, study quality was moderate to low.

Conclusions: Long-term interventions targeting animals and humans can significantly reduce EG transmission, particularly when PZQ is included. Higher-quality evidence, standardized methods, and better reporting on post-intervention outcomes are necessary to draw stronger conclusions and assess the sustainability and scalability of control measures. A One Health approach is essential for integrating and sustaining long-term EG control efforts.

Introduction

Cystic echinococcosis (CE) is a zoonotic disease caused by the tapeworm *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (EG) [1–3]. CE is most prevalent in the Mediterranean area, Eurasia, North and East Africa, and South America, where dissemination is closely linked to home sheep slaughtering and the feeding of raw viscera to dogs [4–7]. However, human CE cases are also reported in the USA [8], Canada [9,10],

Europe [11,12], and Japan [13]. High infection rates among dogs, coupled with socioeconomic and ecological factors, lead to extensive human exposure [14–16]. The global burden of CE includes 184,000 disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) annually, human-associated economic losses of \$764 million per year [17], and a global cost for controlling the disease in animals and humans estimated at \$3 billion [3]. Inadequate reporting of CE cases due to poor surveillance is also common globally and prevents accurate estimates of the burden of

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disease [18]. Despite its widespread distribution and significant global impact on human health, CE is considered a neglected tropical disease, more specifically, a neglected zoonotic disease (NZD) [19–21]. CE does not receive enough attention and funding, which results in limited research efforts compared to other diseases. EG transmission involves mainly canines and ruminants, so research initiatives and intervention approaches are hindered by intersectoral work, complexities associated with ecological factors, and the intricate economics related to animal husbandry [22]. Controlling NZDs offers a cost-effective opportunity to reduce poverty in rural regions where they are most prevalent [23]. Rural determinants of health involve social, psychological, economic, and spiritual aspects that should be specifically addressed in control strategies [24].

EG has a complex life cycle involving definitive hosts, intermediate hosts, and humans as dead-end hosts [3,25]. Intermediate hosts, primarily herbivores like sheep, develop larval cysts in organs such as the liver and lungs after ingesting pastures contaminated with parasite eggs. Definitive hosts, typically domestic or wild canids, become infected by consuming the organs of intermediate hosts containing these cysts [3,25]. In hyperendemic regions, it is common for humans to reside closely with livestock and shepherd dogs, sharing water from natural sources; however, the evidence supporting infection through contaminated water is tenuous [26–31]. In these areas, infected shepherd dogs become the primary source of infection for both humans and livestock [6,15].

Public health control programs focus on preventing CE, primarily aiming to stop the transmission of the causative agent, EG, to hosts [18,32]. Strategies targeting definite or intermediate hosts may include regular dog deworming [33,34], dog population control [35,36], improved management of infected viscera [37], sheep vaccination [38], health education programs [39], epidemiological surveillance strategies [40–42], improvement of diagnostic tests and infrastructure [19,43], and integrative One Health initiatives [44], among others. However, a common barrier to effective control programs is the lack of sufficient information needed to design, implement, and evaluate them.

A scoping review on *Echinococcus granulosus* is both timely and necessary due to persistent gaps in the standardization of diagnostic and control strategies, as well as the fragmented nature of recent evidence. Despite its continued global public health relevance, particularly in endemic regions, there has been limited synthesis of current research trends. This review addresses the need to map the evolving landscape of *E. granulosus* research, identify inconsistencies, and highlight areas where further study or policy attention is warranted. A comprehensive literature review was conducted using a scoping review methodology, a useful tool in the arsenal of evidence synthesis approaches [45]. The goal was to identify the scientific rationale, objectives, and efficacy of various interventions, providing an updated overview of the current status of global EG control efforts. This study provides valuable insights to inform future research and public health initiatives for CE control.

Methods

The protocol of this review is registered on the Open Science Framework (www.osf.io) with DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/48AZR. All available evidence on interventions for EG control was mapped. The Arksey and O'Malley Framework, consisting of five stages, was followed: (i) Identifying the research question, (ii) Identifying relevant studies, (iii) Study selection, (iv) Charting the data, and (v) Collating, summarizing, and reporting the results [45–49].

Identifying the research questions

This review aimed to (i) map all available evidence regarding field interventions aimed at controlling, reducing, or eliminating echinococcosis in endemic areas and (ii) identify research gaps that could lead

to future studies and, potentially, successful interventions. The following questions guided this review:

1. What strategies have been implemented, piloted, or tested to reduce, control, or eliminate EG infection in animals and/or humans?
 - a. What was the rationale for the study/intervention?
 - b. Who/what were the targets?
 - c. What barriers and facilitators were encountered?
2. For each intervention found in question 1:
 - a. What was the efficacy/effectiveness outcome?
 - b. Was there any safety metric/outcome?
 - c. How long has the program/intervention been in place? Is it still ongoing?
 - d. What kind of modifications/changes has the intervention undergone over time?

Identifying relevant studies

A search strategy for databases and search engines for published data was initially outlined, followed by reference scanning and a gray literature search for unpublished or difficult-to-find studies. For published data, MEDLINE (via PubMed), EMBASE, SCOPUS, Web of Science, Global Index Medicus, and Google Scholar were included. The search strategy was outlined by the research team with the support of a librarian (Appendix 1: search strategy). The search included all studies published up to May 2024. The results from all searches were imported and organized in Covidence™ (Melbourne, Australia), a web-based software platform that streamlines the literature review process.

Study selection

All available evidence was included, including published, preprint, and gray literature, evaluating interventions to reduce, control, or eliminate echinococcosis caused by EG infections in animals and humans. The search was global; studies were not restricted by region. Publications in English, Spanish, and Portuguese were included. Studies that included vaccines as components of field interventions were included. However, studies whose primary endpoint was to evaluate the efficacy of vaccines or deworming treatments under controlled conditions were considered out of scope, as the focus was on real-world implementation and broader population-level outcomes rather than results from tightly regulated experimental settings (e.g., vaccine clinical trials, laboratory-based studies).

The articles were screened in two stages: first, by titles and abstracts, and second, by full-text. Titles and abstracts were imported into Covidence™, where reviewers assessed eligibility and filtered duplicates. The final list was evaluated by two pairs of reviewers. Both screening processes were preceded by a pilot to compare the results of the review teams, align the criteria, and discuss discrepancies to reach a consensus. The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) was used for quality appraisal, as it allows the evaluation of multiple types of studies [50].

Data charting, synthesis, and reporting results

An electronic form/Excel® spreadsheet was developed by the research team for the full-text stage for reviewers' referencing, tracking, and documentation of excluded studies. Key information recorded included, but was not limited to, author(s), year of publication, methodology, and intervention characteristics. The abstraction chart was piloted to assess consistency between reviewers and calibrate the chart if needed.

The included papers were divided into types of intervention and classified according to the associated control mechanism (elimination of parasites, population control of hosts, and management of sick human/animal populations, among others) and their target host. If

available, the efficacy or effectiveness and safety outcomes, the associated variables, and the barriers/facilitators were described for each type of intervention. The results are presented in figures and tables. For studies with qualitative results, a synthesis of the main variables is presented.

Given the number of studies in each category and the variation in methodologies, summarizing the findings into broad conclusions would risk oversimplifying key details. Several studies lacked information on intervention implementation, target populations, or sustainability, which made comparisons difficult. A condensed synthesis could obscure critical differences in study contexts and outcomes, limiting the ability to derive meaningful conclusions applicable to different settings. Therefore, each study is presented individually in detailed tables to preserve the nuances of their findings and methodological diversity.

Quality appraisal

The MMAT was used, which allows for the appraisal stage of reviews that include qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods studies. It presents two general questions followed by five sections corresponding to different study designs, each section having five questions that evaluate quality criteria [50,51]. Each question can be answered as "yes," "no," or "can't tell". A "yes" is considered the fulfillment of the criterion. The tool does not present a cut-off point, so the score of the studies was presented descriptively, as suggested by *Reporting the Results of the MMAT (version 2018)* [52], as follows:

- 5***** or 100 % quality criteria met
- 4**** or 80 % quality criteria met
- 3*** or 60 % quality criteria met
- 2** or 40 % quality criteria met
- 1* or 20 % quality criteria met

In the case of mixed studies, the recommendation of the MMAT manual was followed: we asked a total of 15 questions (five questions for qualitative studies, five for quantitative studies, and five for mixed studies) and considered the lowest score as the overall quality score.

Results

A total of 7853 potentially relevant studies were found, with 2848 from MEDLINE, 2139 from Scopus, 1347 from the World Health Organization, 828 from Web of Science, 580 from Google Scholar, 108 from Embase, and three from gray literature. A total of 1997 duplicates were removed either manually or identified by Covidence. After screening the titles and abstracts, 309 met the eligibility criteria. Subsequently, 264 studies were excluded during full-text review, and finally, 45 studies were included in this scoping review (Figure 1). These studies were mapped across various regions globally, as depicted in Figure 3. Most of these studies were conducted in Argentina and China (n = 7 each), where there are high endemicity areas. Other highly endemic areas, such as Turkey and Kenya, have been the subject of at least one study each. However, several other hyperendemic regions around the world have yet to be represented in the literature.

Interventions in humans

Of the 45 articles reviewed, seven studies reported interventions aimed only at humans (Table 1). Six studies primarily focused on education and awareness, and one study focused on CE monitoring. In Portugal, a 13-year program identified 62 CE cases via ultrasound, 24 cases via serology, and 21 cases via both methods. Health information was provided to adults, with specific activities designed for children. CE prevalence decreased by 20 % midway through the study, and by the end, feeding raw viscera to dogs had dropped from 60 % to 20 % [53].

In Peru, nine educational sessions were provided to 28 schoolchildren. High-level knowledge of CE increased from 50 % to 100 % in the intervention group [54]. In Chile, a 7-level educational intervention conducted over 4 years for 3145 participants aged 2–20 improved knowledge at all levels. Compared to urban schools, rural schools showed greater improvement. The most significant changes were in knowledge about hand washing, washing fruits and vegetables, and avoiding dog licking. Knowledge of responsible dog ownership was highest before the intervention and showed the least change [55]. In the USA, a 73-item questionnaire was used to evaluate an educational program, including knowledge and willingness to engage in preventive actions. Over 8 years, awareness increased from 28 % to 83 % [56]. In Turkey, awareness interventions targeted children, the general public, and healthcare professionals. Among children, knowledge increased from 5.8 % to almost 90 %. No efficacy measure was provided for adults [39]. In Morocco, an integrated health messaging intervention included EG, rabies, and other zoonoses. "Piggy-backing" on high-priority diseases like rabies allowed participants to better retain information on EG [57]. In Argentina, an ultrasound monitoring trial in humans supported a comprehensive control program. The trial showed that prevalence decreased from 5.5 % to 4.04 %. Additionally, high-risk groups were identified, and this evidence informed program actions [58]. Details about these interventions focused on humans are provided in Table 1.

Interventions in animals

Twenty-one articles reported interventions aimed only at animals (Table 2). Six interventions targeted both dogs and sheep, 12 targeted only dogs, and three targeted only sheep. Most studies involved the delivery of praziquantel (PZQ). In Australia, an intervention included testing dogs, treating positive dogs with bunamide at days 0 and 14, and making recommendations for home slaughtering. The incidence in dogs dropped from 11.3 % to 2.1 % over a 4-year period [59]. In Uruguay, different PZQ treatment frequencies in dogs were compared. One year of treatment every 6 weeks reduced the prevalence in lambs to 0 %, while in the 12- and 16-week schemes, as well as in the control group, prevalence ranged from 4.3 % to 18.6 % [60]. Also in Uruguay, a 9-year PZQ-based control program in dogs reduced prevalence in dogs from 22.7 % to 1.5 %, and in 4-year-old sheep from 49.3 % to 18.5 % [61]. Similarly, in Brazil and China, dogs treated with PZQ every 30 days had prevalence reduced from 10.67 % to 0.74 % [62] and from 7.3 % to 1.7 % [63], respectively. In Peru, an unusual PZQ regimen was implemented: two treatment cycles were administered to dogs with a 12-month interval between them. In each cycle, dogs received three doses of PZQ, one per month. Prevalence in dogs reduced from 47.2 % to 1.3 %. Unfortunately, prevalence was evaluated only once, 1 month after the last dose [64]. In Argentina, a control program that began in 1980 underwent multiple modifications. It started with an EG baseline for dogs, sheep, and the environment. Later, lambs received the EG95 vaccine and multiple boosters. Female sheep received an extra dose for colostral immunity. After 3 years, prevalence in sheep dropped from 26.2 % to 7.8 % [65]. This program, updated in 2009, was later evaluated through copro-enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) in dogs, necropsy of adult sheep, and ultrasound screening in children. By 2017, infection rates in 6-year-old sheep decreased from 56.3 % to 21.6 %, in dogs from 9.6 % to 3.7 %, and in children from 38 cases to only one [66]. In the same program, between 2018–2022, in addition to EG95 vaccination in sheep, dogs were treated with PZQ 4 times a year. Prevalence among vaccinated and unvaccinated sheep was 21 % and 66 %, respectively [67]. In Chile, a neighboring country to Argentina, a 3-year program vaccinated sheep with EG95 at 2 and 3 months old, then annually. By the end of the program, cyst fertility dropped from 28.1 % to 8 % [68]. Another multi-pronged intervention in Morocco, conducted over 4 years, compared PZQ for dogs every 4 months, EG95 vaccination of lambs, and both combined. Dog prevalence dropped

Figure 1. Flowchart of the inclusion/exclusion process for studies on EG control interventions. EG, *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato*; WHO, World Health Organization.

from 35 % to 9 %. Post-intervention, the prevalence of viable cysts in sheep was 5 % with combined intervention, 8 % with sheep vaccination, 69 % with dog treatment only, and 77 % with no intervention [69].

Cyprus and Norway provided data from hypoendemic areas. In Norway, dogs were treated with PZQ biannually at first, and annually in subsequent years. After 4 years, prevalence in reindeer decreased from 1.5 % to 0.11 % [70]. In Cyprus, infected livestock were identified in slaughterhouses, dogs were tested using arecoline and coproELISA, and infected dogs were either euthanized and examined or treated with PZQ. Sheep prevalence declined from 0.033 % to 0.007 % [71]. Several studies did not report efficacy metrics or reported negative results. In Kenya, a 16-month control program included dog population control, administration of arecoline, and treatment of infected dogs with PZQ every 6 weeks. Prevalence decreased but remained high and returned to pre-control levels within 3 months [72]. In Kyrgyzstan, dogs were treated with PZQ four times over 1 year. Pre-intervention coproELISA prevalence was 20.1 %; however, post-intervention prevalence was not reported [73]. In China, several studies have been reported. Baits with

PZQ were tested to treat dogs and other canids every other month; however, after 7 months, no significant effect was observed in high-prevalence areas [74]. In Buddhist areas, where dog culling is not accepted, administering PZQ twice a year for 5 years reduced EG prevalence in dogs only from 27 % to 20 % [75]. In another study, after 3 years of implanting slow-released PZQ-medicated bars in dogs, coproELISA positivity dropped from 41.2 % to 3 %, seropositivity in children declined from 41.2 % to 5.4 %, and prevalence in sheep decreased from 44.8 % to 10.7 % [76]. Some interventions explored innovative approaches. In China, smart collars enabled automatic delivery of PZQ baits to dogs. These collars also included sensors to provide real-time data that could be used to study trends in echinococcosis. Post-intervention prevalence was not provided [77]. In Italy, carcass disposal was improved through vulture feeding stations. CE prevalence in sheep was 65.3 %. Although no post-intervention estimates were provided, the authors concluded that the program reduced CE risk and burden [78]. Also in Italy, GPS data loggers were attached to a lead sheep and two shepherd dogs to define grazing areas. The

Table 1
Interventions in humans.

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
Trials										
1	Larrieu et al. [58]	Argentina	Field trial	689 people.	542 asymptomatic volunteers and 147 asymptomatic cohabitants of CE cases.	Control and prevention	Portable ultrasound screening in general public and cohabitants of CE cases that overwent surgery, with a 3-year gap during the national control program. Prevalence was reported. Tracking of CE cases in three phases. - Phase 1: Epidemiological questionnaires to volunteers. - Phase 2: Obtaining a blood sample for serological testing. - Phase 3: Abdominal ultrasound. This actions included the distribution of informative brochures along with explanation of their content, small informational sessions for general population and specific activities for school-age children.	3 years (1984–1986)	Prevalence of CE in humans.	Yes
2	Hernández Mira et al. [53]	Portugal	Field trial	2152 people.	Rural volunteers: 780 men and 1362 women.	Eradicate	Educative program: nine in-person sessions of 2.5 h weekly. The program, using the Bustos operative didactic model, employed various techniques and teaching materials like small group sizes, guidance, active student participation throughout the learning sessions, self-correction of answers by students, and reinforcement at the end of each session. After the intervention a questionnaire of 40 items was applied to assess effectivity. Educative program: First, areas of knowledge about CE were defined and seven educational levels were differentiated by grade of education. A didactic guide	13 years (1994–2006)	Prevalence of CE in humans. Change in people's habits.	Yes
3	Pariona-Diaz et al. [54]	Peru	Pre post	56 people.	Experimental and control group, both of 28 boys and girls from 5th grade from a public school in Huancavelica.	Prevention	Educative program: nine in-person sessions of 2.5 h weekly. The program, using the Bustos operative didactic model, employed various techniques and teaching materials like small group sizes, guidance, active student participation throughout the learning sessions, self-correction of answers by students, and reinforcement at the end of each session. After the intervention a questionnaire of 40 items was applied to assess effectivity. Educative program: First, areas of knowledge about CE were defined and seven educational levels were differentiated by grade of education. A didactic guide	9–10 weeks	Knowledge level about CE after the implementation of the educational program.	Yes
4	Castillo-Montes et al. [55]	Chile	Pre post	3145 people.	Students from preschool, primary and secondary. All schools from three communes were included.	Prevention and Control	Educative program: First, areas of knowledge about CE were defined and seven educational levels were differentiated by grade of education. A didactic guide	5 years (2014–2018)	Changes in the knowledge level about CE after the educational program.	No

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Table 1 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
5	Observational Condie et al. [56]	USA	Cross-sectional	People from 156 households.	Adult members of each family from Fountain Green, Utah.	Prevention and control	with different objectives and methodologies was assigned to each level. Teachers were trained to develop the program in three sessions (initial, profundization, closure). Seven pre and post tests previously validated were applied before the first and after the last session. A 73-item questionnaire was constructed to investigate the impact of an educational-control program. The questionnaire included information about CE and the relationship between antecedent variables and the willingness to engage in six preventive actions: - medicating dogs regularly, attending screening clinics, tying up their dogs, preventing dogs from eating sheep liver and lungs, disposing sheep carcasses in covered pits and bury or burn sheep carcasses.	3 weeks (August 1978)	Correlation of attitudes and knowledge, and the willingness to participate in the public health control program.	No
6	Ducrottoy et al. [57]	Morocco	Convergent	656 people for focus groups. 6910 people for evaluation questionnaire and pop quiz. 33 teachers for evaluation forms. 23 teachers for interviews.	Three groups in rural areas of Sidi Kacem province: - Community, including women, men and children, - School children, and, - Stakeholders, including NGOs, healthcare professionals and local governments.	Prevention	For the community group, educational events focused on rabies, CE, leishmaniasis, brucellosis and bovine tuberculosis. They tried different combinations of these diseases. For events that focus solely on bacterial zoonosis, there was a separation between adults of 21 communes and school children from 23 schooled-bases. Education of stakeholders took place in participatory workshops and four education sessions of integrated messaging on all five zoonosis.	18 months	Pros and cons of the integrated health messaging intervention.	No

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Table 1 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
7	Altintas et al. [39]	Turkey	Descriptive	5208 people.	Three target groups from CE endemic districts: - Elementary school third and fourth year students, teachers and administrators from schools, - General public, and, - Healthcare professionals.	Prevention	Evaluation was done in focus groups, post presentation pop quizzes, and evaluation questionnaires. In schools, evaluation forms were given to teachers and headmasters, and informal interviews were held with teachers. Awareness activities: Student adapted presentations were given in 26 schools for students, teachers and administrators. Brochures and posters were distributed. For general public seminars and brochure distribution about CE. Training of healthcare professionals included presentations and distribution of brochures.	1 year (2019–2020)	Number of attendees to the seminars. Knowledge changes in school children.	No

CE: cystic echinococcosis; EG: *Echinococcus granulosus*.

Table 2

Interventions in animals.

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
Trials										
1	Meldrum and McConnell [59]	Australia	Field trial	Dogs per years: - 1964/65: 1552. - 1965/66: 8013. - 1966/67: 18,900. - 1967: 9394.	Dogs from municipalities all over Tasmania.	Control, Prevention reduction	Tasmanian control scheme included a method of testing dogs that involved the use of testing strips on mobile laboratories. Also recommendations were given to owners against feeding offal to dogs and favoring good practices for home slaughters. Obligatory treatment with bunamide of positive dogs and repeated in 14 days.	4 years (1964–1967)	EG incidence in dogs.	Yes
2	Kummeneje et al. [70]	Norway	Field trial	42,591 reindeer livestock and unknown number dogs.	Reindeer livestock. Dogs from reindeer owners.	Eradication	Systematic PZQ treatment of dogs owned by reindeer breeders and posterior public meat inspection of reindeer.	7 years (1975–1981)	EG prevalence in reindeer meat before and after the introduction of dog PZQ treatment.	Yes
3	Macpherson et al. [72]	Kenya	Field trial	452 dogs.	Dogs from rural areas.	Control	The program included registration of owned dogs, elimination at owners request and of stray dogs, dosing of identified dogs every 6 weeks with PZQ, dosing with AB, spaying of female dogs and elimination of infected owned dogs by owners petition.	16 months	Proportion of registered dogs dosed. Number of destroyed dogs.	Yes
4	Economides and Christofi [71]	Cyprus	Field trial	15,528 dogs. 6,103,649 livestock (cattle, sheep, goats and pigs).	Stray dogs and farm dogs from 48 villages and infected livestock from 79 villages.	Control and Eradication	Detection of infected livestock during slaughter by cysts identification and testing of dogs from the infected location. Treatment of infected dogs with PZQ baits. Euthanasia of infected stray dogs and postmortem examination. Additionally, records of human CE cases in government hospitals reported in an unpublished study are referred to observe the dog-human transmission.	7 years (1993–1999)	EG incidence in dogs and livestock.	Yes
5	Cabrera et al. [60]	Uruguay	Field trial	Section 1: 71 dogs and 1036 sheep. Section 2: 451 dogs and 1013 sheep. Section 3: 476 dogs and 696	The area selected was divided in 4 sections that included farms and houses from rural and urban places.	Control	Section 1: no control and continued with the national education program. Owners were free to dose their dogs with PZQ. Sections 2–4: dogs were recorded and treated PZQ every 6, 12, 16 weeks for	2.5 years	EG prevalence in sentinel lambs as the mean number of cysts per infected sheep. % of farms infected and % of sheep infected.	Yes

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Table 2 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
				sheep. Section 4: 237 dogs and 907 sheep.			each section. Sentinel lambs were purchased from farms, followed and examined upon death. Sheep slaughtered for human consumption were also examined for CE. <i>T. hydatigena</i> and <i>ovis</i> were also recorded.			
6	Farias et al. [62]	Brazil	Field trial	First evaluation: 65 dogs. One month after the last treatment: 61 dogs.	Dogs in rural, suburban and urban areas.	Control	Each dog was treated with PZQ regardless of their diagnostic results after first purgation and every 30 days until the 8th month. Purging dogs with AB to observe the presence of EG and coproELISA before and after the treatment. Property owners were asked about treating their dogs, letting them eat raw viscera and open slaughtering facilities.	1.7 years (2001–2002)	Infected dogs before and after PZQ treatment.	Yes
7	Oku et al. [61]	Uruguay	Field trial	Before the program: 79 town dogs, 208 farm dogs and 639 sheep. After the program: 375 sheep.	Town and farm dogs. Sheep viscera from slaughterhouses.	Control	A change in the control program included treatment with PZQ monthly to all dogs. Before the program dogs were examined for adult stage of cestodes by necropsy and fecal examination. Sheep, both before and after the program were examined for cysts.	9 years (1991–1999)	EG prevalence in dogs and sheep before and after the control program.	Yes
8	Wei et al. [76]	China	Field trial	603 dogs in 2000.	Dogs from 22 villages from two experimental areas, one from an agricultural region and the other from a pastoral region from epidemic areas in the north of Xinjiang and an adjacent country with similar conditions for the control area.	Prevention and control	Type SRP III slow release medicated hypodermic bars containing 500 mg of PZQ were implanted in dogs. Then coproELISA was used to detect EG in dogs every year. Serum antibody was used to screen new pupils in a primary school in all the areas and portable ultrasound for children aged 7–16 years in the experimental areas. Also, surveillance in 1 year old lambs from the experimental areas were inspected for EG metacystodes in slaughterhouses.	3 years (2002–2003)	EG prevalence in dogs at the start and annually. EG prevalence in new primary school pupils and school children. Prevalence of EG in sheep.	Yes
9	Yang et al. [75]	China	Field trial	4263 owned dogs.	Dogs from an agricultural area.	Control	Dogs were treated with PZQ twice a year. Dogs from selected households were	6 years (2000–2005)	EG prevalence in dogs, sheep and goats. Characteristics of cysts	Yes

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Table 2 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
				1500-2000 stray dogs.			tested with coproELISA after each treatment. Unwanted dogs were euthanized and inspected for EG worms. Yaks, sheep and goats were examined for cysts. Human and animal cysts were sequenced for <i>apt6</i> gene.		in yaks. DNA analysis of cysts.	
10	Larriou et al. [65]	Argentina	Field trial	Control area: 7128 sheep, 1550 lambs and 141 dogs. Vaccination area: 9383 sheep, 3146 lambs and 311 dogs.	150 farms from different regions in Rto Negro.	Control	Before vaccination, 109 farms were selected for a baseline survey at random and tested with coproELISA/WB (dogs), ELISA/WB (lambs) and PCR (soil). Also necropsies from purchased animals > 6 years, and dogs purgation with AB were done. Sheep from 71 farms were the control group, and, from 79 farms received two immunizations with EG95 (first dose at 30 days of age and second at 60 days of age) and a booster at 1-1.5 years of age. Additionally, 13 (all female animals) from one region were vaccinated with one dose for 2 months period to generate colostrum immunity in lambs born after vaccination. Impact after vaccination was compared between the vaccinated and control groups.	3 years	Vaccination rates and diagnosis of EG after the introduction of EG95 vaccine.	Yes
11	Van Kesteren et al. [73]	Kyrgyzstan	Field trial	2013: 191 dogs. 2014: 193 dogs.	Dogs from 10 Alay Valley communities.	Control	Pre intervention of coproELISA prevalence was determined, followed by intervention of deworming with PQZ four times a year. Local knowledge of CE was measured. PQZ dosing and the impact of the intervention on coproELISA prevalence were evaluated. Two pilot areas, one with manual delivery other with unmanned aerial vehicle delivery. GPS was used to locate and synchronize point for bait. Bait consisted of 8	1 year (2013-2014)	Evaluation of PQZ dosing. EG prevalence in dogs.	Post-intervention EG prevalence in dogs not reported.
12	Yu et al. [74]	China	Field trial	Unknown.	Wild canines from two pilot areas with a total coverage of 0.48 km ² .	Control		6 months	Exploratory outcomes included time consumption and labor, cost of baits and deworming outcome in fecal samples.	EG/CE pre-post frequencies not estimated.

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Table 2 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
13	Larriou et al. [66]	Argentina	Field trial	8483 sheep, 309 dogs.	Sheep and dogs from areas from Mapuche native communities in the province of Rio Negro.	Control	beats of 50 mg of PZQ (400 mg PZQ in total). Fecal samples were collected in same place of bait. EG95 vaccine was used in lambs at 30 days, 60 days and 1–1.5 years old. The program's effectiveness was monitored through various methods, including arecoline test, coproELISA testing and Western blot in dog fecal samples, and ELISA from sera & necropsy of adult sheep. The study also screened children using ultrasound.	8 years (2009–2017)	Sheep vaccination rates. Diagnosis of EG in dogs and sheep after the introduction of EG95 vaccine.	Yes
14	Amarir et al. [69]	Morocco	Field trial	797 lambs, 6545 dogs.	Young female lamb from 32 sheep breeders and owned dogs.	Control	Two different settings took place: In the first one, dogs received 4-monthly treatment with PZQ. In the second, no treatment was given to dogs. Lambs in both cases were randomly allocated in the vaccination or the control group. The vaccination of sheep required two doses, at 2 months old and 1 month later with the EG95 vaccine. They were followed for 4 years with ante mortem ultrasounds or post-mortem dissection.	3.3 years (2015–2019)	Annual EG incidence risk for each group.	Yes
15	Berlinguer et al. [78]	Italy	Field trial	445 griffon vultures	Griffon vultures in an open hilly area where a 4% of European ovine population is present.	Control and prevention	Controlled disposal of caprine, bovine and equine carcasses in implemented supplementary feeding stations, known as "vulture restaurants".	6 years (2015–2020)	Biomass produced from animal cadavers. Costs saved from incineration and carbon emission.	EG/CE pre-post frequencies not estimated.
16	Yang et al. [77]	China	Field trial	523 dogs	Dogs from pastoral areas of three provinces of China.	Control and surveillance	Remote management system based on internet of things as a novel tool to control smart deworming devices to deliver efficient PZQ baits to dogs regularly and automatically and as a smart digital management platform to monitor, analyze, and display the epidemic trends	6 months (2019–2020)	Remote management system performance parameters.	EG/CE pre-post frequencies not estimated.

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Table 2 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
17	Gädick et al. [68]	Chile	Field trial	1st assessment: 223 sheep. 2nd assessment: 200 sheep.	A commune of predominantly Pehuenche indigenous people: nine localities across for the first assessment and 10 localities for the second one.	Prevention	of echinococcosis dynamically, in real time. Administration of EG95 vaccine at 2 months and 1 month after the first dose. Although most received it at 3 months and without the 1 month booster. Sheep 2–4 years old were examined for cysts before and after the vaccination.	5 years (2016–2020)	Frequency of EG infection and fertility of cysts after vaccination compared to frequency of infection before.	Yes
18	Labanchi et al. [67]	Argentina	Field trial	3898 ovine. 3934 caprine. 221 dogs. 58 owners.	Indigenous reservation areas.	Control	EG95 vaccine in 2 initial doses 1 month apart starting at 30 days old and a booster around 1–1.5 years old. Sheep and goat CE diagnosis by necropsy and serology (ELISA). Dogs were dosed with PZQ 4 times a year. Surveys among farmers about slaughter habits for human consumption.	5 years (2018–2022)	EG prevalence in adult goats and sheep. Sheep vaccination rates.	Yes
19	Montalvo et al. [64]	Peru	Field trial	252 dogs	Owned and stray dogs.	Control	At the start of the intervention, fecal samples from owned dogs and stray dogs were analyzed by microscopic examination and coproELISA. Dogs received two 3-dose cycles of PZQ every 30 days in a 2 year period. Stray dogs were dosed combining PZQ with bread or chicken and identified using photos. Prevention messages and informative material were provided to owners in each home visit. Stool samples were collected and analyzed 1 month after the last PZQ dose.	2 years (2018–2019)	EG prevalence in dogs before and after the intervention.	Yes
20	Wang et al. [63]	China	Field trial	2017: 184,564 dogs. 2018: 175,561 dogs. 2019: 171,754 dogs.	Domestic and stray dogs from 74 CE endemic districts.	Control	Collection of data on domestic dog registration and deworming. Dog owners embedded PZQ in food to give dogs and recorded it on a logbook every month. Stray dog sheltering. Fecal samples from domestic dogs randomly collected to identify echinococcus using coproELISA.	3 years (2017–2019)	Number of domestic dogs registered. Stray or infected dogs arrested or sheltered. Dog infection rates.	Yes

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Table 2 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
21	Nocerino et al. [79]	Italy	Field trial	Approx. 200 sheep and dogs per each farm.	Sheep and dogs from 40 sheep farms.	Control	All sheep were tested by ultrasound and post-mortem examinations. There were 5 control farms and 5 CE positive farms received the following interventions. Dogs were treated with chewable tablets of PZQ and milbemycin oxime every 2 months. After 48 h fecal samples were collected individually using the Fill-FLOTAC and analyzed by copromicroscopy. If a sample was positive to Taeniidae eggs, rt-PCR was used to detect EG. Three types of GPS data logger collars were attached to the "flock-leader" sheep and to two shepherd dogs to monitor their movements for 1 month. The area of movement was delimited, and the perimeters were baited with anthelmintic for stray or unowned dogs near the grazing area.	Not specified	EG prevalence in dogs. Identification of points for PZQ delivery. Spatio-temporal distributions of sheep and dogs.	Yes

AB: arecoline bromhidrate; CE: cystic echinococcosis; EG: *Echinococcus granulosus*; ELISA: enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; PZQ: praziquantel.

perimeters of these areas were baited with anthelmintics for free-roaming dogs, offering another method of control [79]. Details of these interventions focused on animals are provided in Table 2.

Interventions in animals and humans

Seventeen articles focused on both animals and humans (Table 3). Multiple long-term programs and short-term studies are reported from South America and describe integrated interventions including dosing dogs, vaccinating sheep, educating and screening humans, and enhancing abattoir surveillance. In Argentina, dogs received PZQ more frequently in high-risk areas and were monitored using arecoline and *in situ* analysis. Education was provided to schools, homes, and rural populations through accessible media. Sheep were inspected at abattoirs, and surveillance data collection improved. After 2 years, dog prevalence decreased from 31.5% to 4.24% [80]. After 17 years of implementation, new human cases in children under 11 decreased by 77% [81]. Also in Argentina, ultrasound surveys in children and coproELISA surveys in dogs were used to identify hotspots of transmission and strengthen control program activities (education, diagnosis and treatment in humans, deworming of dogs, and vaccination of sheep). Dog prevalence reduced from 32% to 15.6% [82]. In Uruguay, a rural intervention included monthly PZQ plus broad-spectrum anthelmintics 1–3 times a year, coproELISA diagnosis, free dog castration, and ultrasound diagnosis for people. Ultrasound training and EG education were provided at health centers, and routine surveillance was conducted in abattoirs. Over 5 years, dog prevalence dropped from 10% to 1.6% [35]. In Chile's Aysen region, from 1982 to 2001, dogs were usually dosed every 6 weeks. Human prevalence decreased from 75% to 32% and sheep prevalence from 90% to 9%. In 2020, sheep vaccination was added, and surveillance was enhanced by examining sheep cysts and by communities reporting cysts via WhatsApp. Cyst size was negatively correlated with vaccination status [83]. In another study in Chile, infected dogs were identified and treated with PZQ. Health education was provided to farm family members, and they were asked to pledge to educate their neighbors, to practice what was learned, and to buy PZQ as a group for their dogs. Serology was conducted on dog owners. Unfortunately, only pre-intervention prevalence was reported [84]. In the US, a decade-long control program in Utah involved PZQ treatment for dogs (frequency unspecified), educational initiatives through press releases, filmstrips, and children's coloring books, diagnostic clinics for humans and dogs, and surveillance and proper disposal of viscera at abattoirs. Over 7 years, infection rates in dogs dropped from 28% to 1%, but later rose to 10% due to some dog owners' noncompliance. Concurrently, EG infection in sheep steadily declined, and public knowledge about the disease significantly increased [85].

Studies and programs from other parts of the world used a similar integrative approach. In New Zealand, a 21-year program involved treating dogs regularly with arecoline, banning raw offal feeding, and promoting safe sheep slaughtering practices. The authors used the age at which 20% of lambs had 'parasitic' liver damage as an efficacy metric. Over the trial, this age increased from 4 to 9 months [86]. In Cyprus, education was carried out over 5 years, targeting schoolchildren, housewives, and dog owners. Dogs were screened, and infected dogs were euthanized or treated with arecoline according to the owner's consent. After 3 years, dog prevalence dropped from 50% to 6.8% [87]. In Wales and Morocco, education alone was compared to education plus PZQ. In Wales, after the intervention, lamb prevalence was 4.3% in the education area, 6% in the education plus PZQ area, and 10.4% in the control area. Education significantly increased PZQ usage among farmers [88]. In Morocco, an integrated intervention targeted dog rabies, echinococcosis, and canine leishmaniasis. Dogs were treated three times a year and purged with arecoline at the end of the study. Dogs receiving PZQ had lower infection rates than those in the education-only arm, but the difference was not statistically significant. Education increased knowledge but did not affect risky

behaviors [89]. In Spain, dogs were treated with PZQ every 6 weeks for 6 years. Health education targeted high-risk groups for the first 3 years, and stray dogs were removed. Sheep were inspected, and sanitary pits were provided to dispose of carcasses. New human cases decreased from 19 to 4 per 100,000 people [90]. Also in Spain, a comprehensive program is reported, though it lacks detailed descriptions of each component. Nonetheless, the program achieved an overall efficacy of 67% and, importantly, reported a profitability of 970% [91]. In China, in hyperendemic areas, a combination of monthly PZQ, culling unwanted dogs, restructuring and training of the EG management teams, and public education reduced prevalence in dogs from 14.7% to 18.6% to zero after 4 years [92]. Another intervention consisted of education, improved sanitation, ultrasound screening of humans, surgical and albendazole treatment, and management and monthly PZQ for dogs. Interestingly, the authors reported measures of efficacy different from disease burden. After 11 years, surgeries rose by 32.4%, albendazole treatment by 81.3%, and dog deworming by 58.6% [93]. In Italy, an 8-year program used sentinel sheep abattoirs, analyzed national slaughterhouse data annually, treated farm dogs with PZQ, and diagnosed dogs with molecular and fill-FLOTAC techniques. Livestock were diagnosed with ultrasound, and human CE surveillance was based on medical records. Public health education was delivered through multiple media formats. The program reduced sheep prevalence by 30%, and all dogs were negative 50 days post-PZQ [44]. In the Falklands, legally imposed control activities between 1965 and 1981 included purging dogs, banning offal feeding, and enforcing shepherd dog movement restrictions. Dogs were treated with PZQ every 6 weeks. Education was conducted through various media formats. Sheep prevalence dropped from over 40% to below 1% by 1993 [94]. Details of these interventions focused on animals and humans can be found in Table 3.

In Figure 2, the points within the EG life cycle are illustrated where different studies aimed to interrupt transmission. As numerous studies implemented multiple interventions targeting various components of the life cycle, the count of interventions depicted in Figure 2 exceeds the total number of papers analyzed.

Quality appraisal

Of the 45 studies reviewed, 40 were evaluated with the quantitative non-randomized studies questions (section 3 of MMAT). The average fulfillment of the quality criteria was 57%: five studies [59,70,83,86,91] did not meet any criteria or their compliance could not be determined, three [58,71,88] met 20%, one [84] met 40%, 16 studies [44,54,61,62,65,72,73,75,78,80,81,87,89,90,93,94] met 60%, 14 studies [35,55,60,63,64,66,67,74,76,77,79,82,85,92] met 80%, and only one study [68] met 100% of the quality criteria. The main criterion for noncompliance or undetermined compliance was the evaluation of possible confounding factors; only one study [68] fully addressed them. The second most frequent challenge was determining representativeness; sampling estimates or clear descriptions of sample selection were not always provided. Another criterion with inadequate or undetermined responses was the completeness of the outcome data. Three studies were evaluated with the quantitative descriptive study questions (section 4 of MMAT). The average overall quality was 47%; one [39] met 20% of the criteria, one [53] met 40%, and one [56] met 80%. The main criterion for compliance was the evaluation of the risk of nonresponse bias, and the information provided was found insufficient to comply with the criterion. The second most frequent problem was the evaluation of representativeness. The three studies described their target population and eligibility, but in two [39,53], it was difficult to determine if their sample was representative. One study [69] was evaluated with the quantitative randomized controlled trials questions (section 2 of MMAT), and it met 60% of the quality criteria. In this study, the information provided was insufficient to fully evaluate whether the randomization was appropriately performed, and no

Table 3
Interventions in humans and animals.

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
Trials										
1	Gemmell [86]	New Zealand	Field trial	Approx. 20,000 sheep, 60 dogs and people in the area.	11 farms in an isolated area with certain natural boundaries.	Control	In the first period, for 9 years, all dog owners were requested not to feed any raw offal to dogs and dogs were treated with AB every 3 months. Farmers were advised to build dog-proof sheep killing facilities and burying carcasses. In the second period of 6 years, there was no supervision of dog dosing, but AB was available. In the third period of 6 years, dogs were dosed with AB every 3 months and feces were examined for tapeworms. Additionally modern mass media education and distribution of posters and brochures was done.	21 years (1943–1963)	Efficacy metric: age at which 20% of lambs had 'parasitic' liver damage.	Yes
2	Polydorou [87]	Cyprus	Field trial	Approx. 45,000 dogs at the start of the campaign and people in the area.	Owned and stray dogs, and people from 39,473 households of 600 villages on an island.	Eliminate	Education to the public through mass communication media, establishment of mobile exhibitions, lectures, and others. Also training of government employees, slaughterers and farmers. Dog control by extermination of stray dogs, spaying of bitches, registration and annual fees for owned dogs, and surveillance (mobile and static laboratory testing screening and diagnosis at owners request). Control of slaughter by legislation to require abattoirs to be approved, inspection of viscera and adequate disposal of infected viscera. Education was attained through press releases, distribution of pamphlets, talks with civic and church groups, counseling during screenings and children adapted filmstrip and coloring book. Pre and post tests were applied to students before and	15 years (1971–1985)	Improvement of people's preventive practices. Eliminated stray dogs. Infection rates in dogs. Number of spayed bitches. Rates of infected slaughtered animals. Functioning abattoirs.	Yes
3	Andersen et al. [85]	United States	Field trial	Approx. 1950 dogs and 90,400 sheep. 49 coyotes. 74 deer.	Dogs and sheep from an agricultural area.	Control	Control of slaughter by legislation to require abattoirs to be approved, inspection of viscera and adequate disposal of infected viscera. Education was attained through press releases, distribution of pamphlets, talks with civic and church groups, counseling during screenings and children adapted filmstrip and coloring book. Pre and post tests were applied to students before and	11 years (1971–1981)	Infection rates in dogs and sheep. CE incidence in humans. Attitudes and practices of dog/sheep owners. Efficacy of coloring	Yes

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Table 3 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
4	Gimeno Ortiz et al. [91]	Spain	Field trial	2544 dogs. Unknown number of livestock and humans.	Stray dogs, livestock in slaughterhouses and people from the provinces of Cáceres and Basajoz of Extremadura.	Control	<p>after receiving the coloring book. Prophylactic treatment of dogs with bunamidine hydrochloride in 1974–1978 and PZQ in 1979–1981. Surveillance: Dogs were purged with AB and examines on site. Sheep were checked for cysts by state meat inspectors and if suspected, confirmed in a parasitology lab. Coyotes and deer were examined to assess them as sylvatic reservoirs. Immunodiagnostic clinics for people were usually held with dog clinics.</p> <p>A control program was implemented including health promotion through education activities; fight against human CE by enhancing case studies, maps and coordination between health centers; fight against animal CE by improving slaughterhouse infrastructures, inspections and confiscations, and control of livestock and wildlife movement; and, fight against animal echinococcosis by strengthening canine census, stray dog elimination and anti-parasite treatment each 4 months. Additionally they did an economic evaluation.</p>	7 years (1983–1990)	EG incidence in dogs and livestock. Stray dogs captured, escaped, eliminated, tested, given back or adopted. CE incidence in humans. Economic loss of CE.	Yes
5	Larrieu et al. [80]	Argentina	Field trial	Approx. 110,468 people, 5322 dogs at the start of the program.	Urban and rural areas.	Control	<p>Control program with focus on community participation including systematic deworming of dogs with PZQ, surveillance of infection rates in dogs through diagnostic deworming with AB, educational activities in schools, use of mass media for communication, determination of sheep parasitism in slaughterhouses and identification of human CE cases.</p>	13 years (1979–1998)	EG prevalence in dogs, sheep and humans.	Yes

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Table 3 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
6	Lloyd et al. [88]	Wales	Field trial	152 lambs, 336 dogs and farmers.	Two lambs and all dogs from each of 76 farms. Farmers from 263 farms. All from three rural areas.	Control	Lambs were purchased from farms of three areas. Area I, received educational and an anthelmintic control program and transmission had stopped previously. Area II, received educational interventions. Areas III, didn't receive previous interventions. Sheep were slaughtered at approx. 15 months of age and examined for cestodes and lesions were processed histologically. Dogs in all farms were sampled 9 months into the grazing period by coproELISA. Farmers answered a questionnaire about control of sheep diseases, dogs and cats, and sheep movement.	7 years in Areas I and II (1983–1989) Unknown in Area III (1989-?)	Rate of infected/ examined sheep. Rate of dogs positive in coproELISA. Owners reporting deworming of dogs.	Yes
7	Apt et al. [84]	Chile	Field trial	5566 people and 2358 dogs.	Dogs present in each house excluding puppies and pregnant females. People older than 3 years old for CE screening. Farm families, and healthcare, agriculture and education professionals	Prevention and Control	Serological and radiological diagnosis of asymptomatic people, and surgical treatment. Surveillance of dogs by AB purging and visualization of strobiliar form of EG. Dog treatment with PZQ. Interviews to the head of farm families about family and personal history, and knowledge, habits and practices related to CE. Educational interventions for farm families were held for at least one member through games. Pre and post tests were applied. Educational interventions with healthcare, agriculture and education professionals.	5 years (1992–1997)	CE prevalence in asymptomatic humans. EG prevalence in dogs. Knowledge in farm families.	EG/CE frequencies reported as cumulative, not pre-post intervention.
8	Larrieu et al. [81]	Argentina	Field trial	11,915 dogs. Population of 596,154 people.	Rural dogs 13 departments from the Río Negro province were included, with a population of approx. 596,154 people.	Control	Dog registration and PZQ treatment every 60 days in rural and 180 days in urban areas, distributed by owners. Surveillance of dog infection with AB purging. Slaughterhouse surveillance of sheep infection examining viscera. Human CE records and follow-up of new cases in public hospitals, screening	17 years (1980–1997)	EG prevalence in humans and animals. Annual CE incidence.	Yes

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Table 3 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
9	Jimenez et al. [90]	Spain	Field trial	9724 dogs, 6764 sheep for examination at the start of the program. Dogs from 553 to 1040, and sheep from 376 to 1172, examined annually during the program. Human population during the program.	Dogs involved with sheep raising for treatment. Autopsied dogs were given up to program authorities or collected stray and rejected dogs. Sheep upon slaughter.	Control	<p>blood test or ultrasound. Educational plan including healthcare seminars, home visits, and information for elementary schools. Treatment of all registered dogs with PZQ every 45 days, for 6 years. Intense health education campaigns to risk groups during the first 3 years. Municipalities identify and impound stray and unwanted dogs and examine them by autopsies. Inspection of cysts in sheep. Provision of sanitary pits for disposal of dead sheep. Mean annual incidence of CE in humans was estimated.</p>	14 years (1987–2000)	EG prevalence in dogs, humans and sheep.	Yes
10	Zhang et al. [92]	China	Field trial	Area 1: 15,990 dogs. - End: 14,684 dogs. Area 2: 13,322 dogs. - End: 14,230 dogs.	Dogs from two hyperendemic areas.	Control	<p>A village hydatid disease control officer registered dogs to be treated monthly with PZQ. A booklet about CE was distributed and television educational programs were transmitted before treatment. Dogs were purged with AB to estimate EG prevalence. Stray and unwanted dogs were eliminated. Sheep livers and lungs were examined for monitoring in slaughterhouses. Leaders and staff included in the control program were trained and officers received specialized workshops.</p>	3 years in one area (1987–1990) 4 years in the other area (1990–1994)	EG prevalence in dogs. CE prevalence in new born sheep.	Yes
11	Irabedra et al. [35]	Uruguay	Field trial	Over 220,000 dogs and 87,536 people.	All dogs and population from rural areas, small towns and with risk factors suburban areas.	Control	<p>Diagnosis in dogs using coproELISA test. Dogs were treated with PZQ every 30 days. Since 2008 treatment included broad-spectrum anthelmintic (pyrantel pamoate + PZQ + febantel) once a year to all registered dogs and three times a year in areas with critical socio-economic contexts, with risk of other parasitosis. Control of dog population by free surgical castration in both sexes. In 2013 microchips</p>	6 years (2008–2013)	EG prevalence in dogs. Mean of dogs treated with PZQ and broad spectrum anthelmintic. Prevalence of CE in people tested with ultrasonography. Prevalence of EG in livestock.	Yes

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Table 3 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
12	Arezo et al. [82]	Argentina	Field trial	1780 dogs and 34,515 children.	Owned dogs from sheep farms and school children between 6 and 14 years.	Surveillance	<p>were used to identify spayed dogs. Diagnosis in humans using ultrasound surveys. Health education using verbal and visual methods. Surveillance in livestock from slaughterhouse data. CE surveillance in livestock farms through dog stool testing with coproELISA. Ultrasound screening for CE in school children. Data was used to create hot spots of CE.</p>	<p>Three years in the first period (2003–2005) Two years in the second period (2009–2010) Two years in the third period (2017–2018)</p>	<p>Identification of risk areas. CE prevalence in children. EG prevalence in dogs.</p>	Yes
13	El Berbri et al. [89]	Morocco	Field trial	6922 dogs and 2885 people.	Dogs and people from 22 communes, mostly rural.	Control	<p>Integrated control intervention for rabies, canine leishmaniasis and CE. Registration of owned dogs. The control group received only rabies vaccination and an educational campaign. The intervention group received rabies vaccination, anti-sand-fly insecticide collar, deworming with PZQ (month 0, month 6 and month 12), and educational campaign. Sampling for leishmania, AB purging and health education evaluation in both groups. Health education, sanitation improving, ultrasound screening of the human population, surgical interventions and treatment with albendazole. Also deworming registered dogs with monthly PZQ. Economic analysis of the national program.</p>	<p>13 months (2013–2014)</p>	<p>Number of registered dewormed dogs. EG prevalence in dogs. People's knowledge changes. Cost estimates.</p>	Partially, Pre intervention EG prevalence not reported
14	Yu et al. [93]	China	Field trial	173,679 people and 2,691,434 dogs.	Registered dogs and patients diagnosed with CE, alveolar echinococcosis, or both, from pastoral and farming pastoral regions.	Control	<p>Health education, sanitation improving, ultrasound screening of the human population, surgical interventions and treatment with albendazole. Also deworming registered dogs with monthly PZQ. Economic analysis of the national program.</p>	<p>11 years (2004–2014)</p>	<p>Proportion of patients medical or surgically treated. Dewormed registered dogs. Cost analysis.</p>	Yes
15	Cringoli et al. [44]	Italy	Field trial	Phase 1: 549 dogs. Phase 2: 1336 dogs. 417 sheep, 125 goats, 383 cattle and 557 water buffaloes. 168 CE patients.	Dogs from sheep farms. Livestock from slaughterhouses. CE patients from hospital discharge records from 2016 to 2018.	Control	<p>Active and passive surveillance in livestock using geospatial tools for georeferencing. Diagnosis in dogs using the fill-FLOTAC recollection techniques and molecular analysis. Targeted treatment of farm dogs with PZQ, using purpose-built confinement cages. Early</p>	<p>Five years in Phase 1 (2010–2015) Three years in Phase 2 (2016–2018)</p>	<p>EG prevalence in dogs and sheep.</p>	Yes

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Table 3 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
16	West [94]	Falklands	Field trial	Unknown number of dogs, sheep and people,	Owned dogs, butchered sheep and people on the island.	Eradicate	<p>diagnosis in livestock by ultrasonography and post-mortem surveillance in slaughterhouses. Surveillance of CE cases hospital discharge records. Analysis of raw vegetables. Dissemination of educational material to the general public like brochures, gadgets, videos and virtual reality.</p> <p>Tapeworm Eradication Order No.1 (1965) was implemented by purging dogs with arcecoline acetarsol.</p> <p>Order No. 2 (1970) involved restrictions on feeding dogs offal and purging with bunamide hydrochloride. Also restricted dog movements near slaughterhouses and enforced fines for breaking this order.</p> <p>Hydatids Eradication Order (1975) enforced the disposal of offal in dog proof containers and banned them being fed to dogs. Fined dog movement restrictions. In 1977, PZQ dog dosing every 6 weeks was implemented. Also, public education which included slide shows, pamphlets and a news sheet called "Hydatid news", released for 6 years.</p> <p>Hydatids Eradication Order (1981) combined the previous orders. Dog dosing with PZQ every 5 weeks in 2010. Sheep were inspected in slaughterhouses and veterinary offices.</p>	1970-present	EG prevalence in sheep.	Yes
17	Chacón [83]	Chile	Field trial	Unknown number of dogs, sheep and people,	Dogs, sheep and people in the Aysen region.	Control	<p>A control program was implemented from 1982 to 2001 including dog deworming every 45 days, sanitary education, slaughter control and surveillance in slaughterhouses and dogs by purging with AB. Another plan in 2020–2022 included sheep vaccination and deworming of dogs and sheep, sanitary</p>	19 years (1982–2001) Three years (2020–2022)	<p>Rate of infected/ examined sheep.</p> <p>Rate of dogs positive in coproELISA.</p> <p>Owners reporting deworming of dogs.</p>	Report with partial results

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Table 3 (continued)

#	Author, year	Country of study	Study design	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Main objective	Intervention	Intervention duration	Main outcomes	Efficacy post-intervention outcomes reported?
							education, reinforcement of diagnosis capacities involving the community by using WhatsApp groups. Identification of dogs with microchips and sheep with electronic earrings.			

AB: arecoline bromhidrate; CE: cystic echinococcosis; EG: *Echinococcus granulosus*; ELISA: enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; pZQ: Praziquantel.

information about blinding was provided. One study [57] was evaluated with the mixed-methods study questions (Sections 5, 1, and 4 of MMAT) and met 40 % of the overall quality criteria. This mixed-methods study had a predominance of qualitative methods and results. When evaluated by components, it scored 100 % compliance in the qualitative criteria (section 1), 60 % in the mixed-methods criteria (section 5), and 40 % in the quantitative criteria (section 4).

Discussion

Forty-five articles on interventions for the control, prevention, or elimination of EG from all regions were mapped and analyzed (Figure 3). The primary goal of control interventions is to halt the transmission of EG to its hosts. Compared to earlier interventions [72,86,87], recent advances have significantly enhanced EG control. Key developments include the incorporation of the EG95 vaccine for sheep [95], improved diagnostic techniques for early detection in dogs (e.g., ELISA) [96,97], and the use of PZQ for dog treatment [98]. Despite these advances, progress in EG control remains inconsistent, with mixed results reported [99], and overall, limited advancement in endemic regions [100–102]. The articles found were heterogeneous and generally low quality, often lacking clear post-intervention outcomes, which hampers the ability to inform future interventions. Common barriers are often mentioned, but few studies explore real-world barriers and facilitators in depth or address the feasibility of interventions. A major challenge identified is the absence of clear, standardized post-intervention outcomes. Some report innovative strategies but provide limited key metrics or follow-up data to assess impact [73,74,77,84]. As highlighted in Tables 2 and 3, this limits efficacy assessment and comparability, emphasizing the need for consistent outcome reporting in future studies. Additionally, implementation costs are rarely reported, yet cost-benefit analyses are essential for the scalability and sustainability of these strategies [103–105].

Effective EG control requires collaborations, partnerships, and community engagement. The educational interventions reviewed here were aimed at increasing awareness and knowledge among various stakeholders [39,54–57], but did not report measures of long-term impact, nor did they provide a map of key stakeholders in their respective settings. However, the primary value of these interventions may lie in promoting community engagement, which is crucial for the success of control and elimination efforts [106,107]. Future studies could aim to build and examine stakeholder and community engagement for the enforcement and sustainability of control activities.

Among the reviewed studies, those focused solely on interventions in animals were the most numerous, while studies focused solely on interventions in humans were the fewest. However, studies focused on both animals and humans generally had more participants, lasted longer, and covered larger geographical areas. The majority of these articles on integrated strategies described national multi-pronged programs including population screening and diagnosis, sanitation improvement, human and animal treatment, and surveillance, among others. Most of these articles came from a few countries that have been able to sustain these massive efforts to control EG. However, a significant challenge in these control programs is ensuring government commitment [108,109]. These programs require substantial effort and financial investment, funding that should come from government sources such as Ministries of Health and Ministries of Agriculture, and participation from other sectors such as education and environment [109,110]. Short-term programs spanning only a few years are inadequate; CE must be treated as a chronic endemic disease requiring sustained efforts over many years [18,111]. Countries, such as Uruguay and Argentina have been implementing control programs for over 50 years with important successes, but they continue to face challenges despite their long-term commitment [30,112].

Others have conducted reviews on EG and its control. For this review, the PRISMA-ScR framework and the Arksey and O'Malley method

Figure 2. Type of control intervention reported in the selected articles and intervention target within the EG life cycle. EG, *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato*; PZQ, Praziquantel. Intervention results are not included.

Figure 3. Global distribution of EG and cystic echinococcosis and studies. EG, *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato*. Map Source: WHO 2011 [137].

Figure 4. Timeline of the progress of EG control tools and the articles included in this review. [138–142].

were used, focusing on studies in English, Spanish, and Portuguese. Others have used various guidelines and checklists, including PRISMA [15,113], MeSH [26], and Medline [18], to evaluate articles across multiple languages and databases. The MMAT for quality appraisal was applied, while others used RCVS, CASP, and JBI [114]. Despite the lack of detailed methodologies in other reviews, they provide comprehensive summaries of the determinants and control programs associated with EG infection. A review [26] highlighted projects like HERACLES (Human Echinococcosis ReseArch in Central and Eastern Societies) [115,116] and MEmE (Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and EG in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain) [117,118], which have created a comprehensive database with the latest epidemiological data from various regions.

Multiple reviews [18,26,119,120] agreed with this review that sheep vaccination emerged as a promising strategy to complement and reduce the time of the control efforts. However, logistical and financial challenges remain in endemic countries, impacting the effectiveness of these interventions. Similar to our results, others have found that insular EG control programs with strict enforcement measures, such as those in the Falklands and Cyprus [87,94] tend to have higher success, achieving control and even elimination. However, these results have not been replicated in inland interventions, suggesting the insular context played a bigger role in the success of those programs, possibly due to easier disease containment, more manageable host populations, and greater feasibility of enforcing control measures [99]. Key challenges reported in these reviews and also found in our review include reliance on rural dog owners for implementing dog treatment, inadequate funding and staffing of programs, and political instability or insufficient political will [6,18,119]. Other frequently encountered implementation barriers that most studies fail to report include limited surveillance [71,81], the presence of ownerless dogs [60,81,89], and two barriers that are assumed common in many endemic countries: geographic accessibility and the semi-nomadic lifestyle of some communities [73]. The One Health approach is recommended [120–122] and necessary to foster intersectoral collaboration—both locally and internationally—to more effectively address persistent barriers and limitations in the long term [123]. However, beyond collaboration, the success of One Health strategies also hinges on strong government leadership, robust veterinary infrastructure, and alignment with local cultural contexts. For example, Argentina's long-term, government-led program—combining dog deworming, sheep vaccination, and community education—achieved significant reductions in ovine CE over 6 years [80,81]. Similarly, multi-sectoral and culturally tailored strategies implemented in Chile, Morocco, and Cyprus have also proven effective [69,71,83], highlighting the essential role of political will and coordinated, context-sensitive interventions in achieving sustainable control of *Echinococcus granulosus*.

Multiple animal-targeting studies reviewed here have tested and refined interventions for the main definitive EG host, the domestic dogs. Since the development of PZQ (Figure 4), an effective cestocide for the mature and immature adult stages of EG [124], that drug has been the primary intervention for dogs, with treatment schemes varying from monthly to quarterly, depending on the disease burden in the area. Challenges for PZQ effectiveness include maintaining treatment, achieving high coverage, owner compliance, and government enforcement [18,125]. One of the fundamental reasons for not achieving high coverage is the inability to find the dog at the house to receive the treatment. There are innovations and new technologies that are being implemented to tackle some of these barriers. Recent interventions involve advanced tools like geolocation devices to treat hotspots, smart collars for automatic baiting, and dropping PZQ baits with drones [74,77,79], which could improve efficiency and reduce costs in control campaigns. Currently, logistical costs are too high for sustained PZQ-based control programs [126,127]. Some of the studies we reviewed report cost-sharing models, such as payment from dog owners [128],

bulk purchases of PZQ [84], annual registration fee supporting dog-focused interventions [87], or government provision of free PZQ [63,73,81].

From the beginning of PZQ and other oral treatments for dogs, palatability and acceptability studies have been conducted to improve mass use of these drugs [129]. More recent studies have focused on understanding reinfection rates after PZQ [126] and testing slow-release PZQ formulations to reduce frequency of treatment [76,127]. Despite these promising advances, a key limitation remains: translating these tools into resource-limited settings where CE is most prevalent. Future research should focus on strategies to integrate cost-effective diagnostic and treatment tools into existing healthcare and veterinary frameworks in endemic areas. These research approaches would include piloting novel technologies in low-resource settings, identifying financial mechanisms for sustainability, and adapting interventions to local socioeconomic and cultural contexts. For example, an accessible formulation that protects dogs for long periods (similar to what is expected from a vaccine) would be a real game changer. Equally important are studies on stakeholder acceptability of interventions. For example, some studies found conflicting perspectives among breeders and their wives, local authorities, and health providers related to EG control actions [38,130]. To enhance the feasibility, sustainability, and ultimate success of elimination and control programs, it is imperative to conduct implementation research [131,132] studies that delve into the agendas and motivations of various stakeholders [133,134]. Understanding the perspectives and priorities of these stakeholders can increase community engagement and inform the design and implementation of more effective interventions [134]. Active participation from the community ensures better acceptance and adherence to control measures, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility towards the program's goals [135,136]. Without these steps, the benefits of advanced tools will remain largely inaccessible to the regions most affected by CE.

This study had some limitations. The final set of articles included a wide range of study designs and approaches, which led to significant heterogeneity in the data. This heterogeneity made it challenging to summarize findings across studies. Differences in the reported methods and results between studies made the classification of studies especially challenging for the quality appraisal. As with other types of reviews, our scoping review could be susceptible to publication bias, due to unpublished or inaccessible studies. Also, we made a strong effort to balance breadth and depth; however, it is possible we prioritized more breadth making it difficult to synthesize findings comprehensively. A challenge we faced was the reduced number of studies included for full-text review. With sparse data, generalizability may be limited and there may be a risk of over interpreting the significance of findings. Moreover, this limited number of studies impeded identifying trends. Despite these limitations, we conducted a rigorous quality assessment of the included studies and implemented a detailed protocol to reduce subjectivity in study selection and data extraction.

Conclusion

In sum, the literature on the control, prevention, or elimination of *E. granulosus sensu lato* shows key advancements in diagnosis, treatment, and vaccines for the intermediate and definitive hosts. However, progress remains inconsistent, particularly in endemic regions, and many studies lack clear post-intervention outcomes, impeding the ability to inform future programs. Standardization in the study reporting is necessary for the comparability of results and the scaling up of interventions. Effective EG and CE control requires sustained government commitment, funding, and active participation from various sectors, including health, agriculture, and education. Long-term programs are necessary, as demonstrated by the decades-long efforts in Uruguay and Argentina. Innovative strategies, such as geolocation devices and drones for PZQ baiting, show promise but face logistical and financial

challenges. To enhance the feasibility and sustainability of elimination and control programs, implementation research focused on understanding stakeholders' agendas and increasing community engagement is crucial. Multi-pronged integrative One Health approaches are essential for overcoming the logistical, economic, and political challenges of sustaining long-term efforts for EG control.

Author contributions

TAD and JAB contributed equally. Both involved in the design, protocol writing, analysis and interpretation of data, and manuscript drafting. MPR, NM, LOC, AC and CG were involved in the design, retrieval of articles, quality appraisal and reporting of results. LOC, NM and MPR were also involved in manuscript drafting. CMG and CUG gave methodological support in all stages and manuscript drafts and substantial revisions. RCN was involved in all stages from conception of the work to manuscript elaboration, coordination of the team, and approval of the final version of manuscript. All authors read and approved the final version of this manuscript.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study can be accessed publicly in the OSF registries at <https://osf.io/48azr>. Additional data can be requested from the authors. The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the manuscript and its supplementary materials.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ijidoh.2025.100078](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijidoh.2025.100078).

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